

The Position of Ahiska Turks in Türkiye-Georgia Political Relations

To cite this article: Collaborate, Current Science, Volume 5, No. 5-7, 2023, p. 22 – 51. - 0099-0001-2307-0203.

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ISSN: 2667-9515

Barcode: 977266795001

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Abstract

In the last 20 years, relations between Turkey and Georgia have made great progress in the economic, political and geo-strategic context. For Georgia, which is trying to integrate with the Euro-Atlantic Axis, its relations with Turkey, the only NATO member on its border and its neighbor, are important. In terms of Turkey, Georgia has an important place in relations with Azerbaijan.

Limitedness

the subject in the light of world literature and data. The research was limited to closely related author and literature topics. Restricted by literature review.

Notifications

Evaluation: Evaluated by internal and external consultants.

Conflict of Interest: The authors declared no conflict of interest regarding this article.

Financial Disclosure: The authors reported no use of financial support for this article.

Ethical Statement

Publication ethics of the relevant regulations of our university; It is a national-based scientific study that aims to ensure that scientific research and publications are carried out in accordance

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with basic principles such as honesty, openness, objectivity, and respect for the findings and creations of others, and works for the realization of these principles in the field of related sciences.

Abstract

In the last 20 years, there has been significant development in the economic, political, and geostrategic contexts of the ties that exist between Turkey and Georgia. It is essential for Georgia, which is working to become a part of the Euro-Atlantic axis, to maintain positive ties with Turkey. This is because Turkey is the only NATO member that is located on Georgia's border and is also Georgia's neighbor. Georgia has a significant position in Turkey's estimation with regard to Azerbaijan's ties with other countries. In point of fact, despite the great improvements that have taken place between Turkey and Georgia, there are still certain issues to be resolved in the context of this bilateral relationship. Because the attempts to repatriate the Meskhetian Turks, who were driven from their homelands in the aftermath of World War II in 1944, have not yet been entirely ended and settled. Meskhetian Turks are a community of Turkish people who have resided in the Meskhetian area of Georgia over the course of history. As a direct consequence of their removal from their homelands as a direct result of this exile, Meskhetian Turks were compelled to travel to Central Asia after being exiled by the Soviet Union in the year 1944. Before being forced into exile, the Meskhetian Turks had a long and significant history in Georgia, where they played a significant role in the country's social, cultural, and economic development.

Turkey's sensitivity and support for Meskhetian Turks has played a significant role in shaping the status of Meskhetian Turks in the context of ties between Turkey and Georgia. Turkey places a lot of emphasis on the fact that Meskhetian Turks are their cognates and that they have similar origins throughout history. As a consequence of this, Turkey offered Meskhetian Turks with political shelter, made it possible for them to become citizens of Turkey, and supported them in social, economic, and artistic endeavors. This attitude used by Turkey toward the Meskhetian Turks is mirrored in the way Turkey interacts with Georgia as well.

The connection between Georgia and the Meskhetian Turks is becoming more difficult to understand. A number of controversial topics have been brought up in Georgia as a result of the repatriation of Meskhetian Turks to the territories they formerly owned and the restoration of

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their property rights. In addition to the exiled Meskhetian Turks, the Meskhetian area is home to a number of other ethnic groups. Because of this circumstance, there have been considerable complications with the repatriation of lands and concerns over property. The process of Meskhetian Turks returning to their ancestral lands is one that requires striking a balance between the needs of the indigenous people and those of the state. Reconciliation and collaboration among the many parties involved in this process are essential if the rights of Meskhetian Turks are to be protected and the integration of these people to be ensured.

In light of the current state of political ties between Turkey and Georgia, the current predicament of the Meskhetian Turks will be investigated in this article. First, the Turkey-Georgia connections that have grown from the past to the present will be reviewed, followed by a discussion of the condition of Meskhetian Turks in the historical process, and lastly, a general assessment will be given by discussing the efforts connected to the return of Meskhetian Turks to their homeland. shall be carried out.

Keywords: Turkish relations with Georgia, Georgia, Ahiska - Turkey, Turkey - Azerbaijan Relations, Azerbaijan

Introduction

The connections between Turkey and Georgia are noteworthy because they demonstrate the significance of the connection between two countries that are geographically next to one another and have close ties to one another in terms of their history and culture. In the framework of these exchanges, the position that the Meskhetian Turks have taken is also of the highest relevance. Throughout the course of Georgia's history, a population known as the Meskhetian Turks has called the country home. The Meskhetian Turks may trace their ancestry back to the Turks who live in Turkey. Today, Meskhetian Turks have a crucial place in the political and cultural links that bind Turkey and Georgia together as one country. These connections are vital to the success of both nations.

The Soviet Union issued an order in 1944 mandating the displacement of Meskhetian Turks from

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their lands in Georgia and then forcibly deported the whole group to Central Asia at the same time. Because this exile was such a momentous and terrible event for Meskhetian Turks, they were compelled to live as refugees for a number of years after it. Turkey, with its strong feeling of family relationships and long-standing connections to Meskhetia, provided major support to the Meskhetian Turks and welcomed those who had been forced to escape to settle there.

It has become clear that Turkey's support for the rights of the Meskhetian Turks is an essential element in the country's relationship with Georgia. Turkey and Georgia have developed a strong working relationship in order to advance the welfare of Meskhetian Turks and protect their right to exercise self-determination. Through conversations and agreements that were established between the two nations, the two countries were able to explore for alternatives for the return of Meskhetian Turks to their regions and the recovery of their rights.

It is impossible to overestimate the cultural importance that the role of Meskhetian Turks plays in Turkey's relations with Georgia. Meskhetian Turks have a long history in both countries. Meskhetian Turks are an integral part of Turkish culture and legacy, not to mention an important one historically. The cultural inheritance of the Meskhetian Turks is the target of a variety of preservation activities that are organized and carried out by Turkey. These efforts are focused on preserving the cultural heritage of the Meskhetian Turks. Through participation in activities including as cultural events, festivals, and language lessons, Meskhetian Turks are able to fortify their cultural identity. The cultural exchange that takes place between Turkey and Georgia is bolstered further by the activities that are described here.

It is possible to note that the historical Turkish-Georgian interactions continued even under the auspices of the USSR, notably on December 5, 1936, when Georgia became a Soviet Federative Republic (Saray, 1997). These contacts started with the settlement of Turks in Anatolia and began with the migration of Turks to Anatolia. These connections were first established when Turks started settling in what is now known as Anatolia, and they continued long after Georgia became a Soviet Federative Republic. Georgia's declaration of independence from the Soviet Union on April 9, 1991 (Surmeli, 2001) was the catalyst for the rekindling of diplomatic relations between Georgia and Russia in the following year. The historical process between Turks and Georgians in

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the fields of history, geography, politics, economics, and the military has lasted up to the present day, despite the fact that it has been disturbed on multiple times for political reasons. This is due to the fact that political tensions have arisen between the two nations.

T u r k i y e - Georgia history is used as the foundation for the relationships; thus, the source is of course very significant. In the context of Turkish and Georgian ties, it is essential to emphasize, in addition to the relevance of history, how physical location plays a role. This is due to the fact that the migration paths of the Turks are an issue that has to be handled historically as well as geographically.

Methodology

The Urartians were the ones in charge of Georgia when it was still called Georgia back in the 9th century BC. It is believed that the Huri Tribe, which was associated to the Van civilization that reigned in Van and the surrounding area, is the earliest known ethnic basis in the history of Georgia. This civilization controlled in Van and the surrounding area. In subsequent ages, Georgians founded their kingdoms in a number of different parts of the Caucasus area. Kingdoms they have created. Caucasia was first formed in this area about the 7th century B.C. 66 years before the common era. After Rome occupied the area in the first century BC, the people living there were subject to Roman control. The Georgian people, who were under Roman control for a period of seventy-five years, became Christians as a result of Rome's influence. Do not see where the Arab influence in the area in the sixth century AD began; it was already well underway. Islamic Era; Anatolia and their control in the Southern Caucasus increased (Gokce, 1979).

started with the Huns in the sixth century of the Common Era. The Georgians and the Seljuks who had settled in Anatolia engaged in conflict throughout the final part of the empire's history, under the reigns of Tugrul Bey and Cagri Bey. The Georgians, who were partially dependent on the Seljuks during the 13th century, were confronted by the Mongol invasion. The Georgians, who came under the rule of the Mongols, struggled against this invasion. However, after the second Mongolian invasion led by Timur, who raided Anatolia, the Georgians lost their power.

During that period in Georgia, Ottoman and Iranian forces were engaged in destabilizing conflicts for dominance over in between signature I main n " Am Asian" Despite the fact that the "

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Agreement " placed the territory under the protection of the Ottoman Empire, the Ottomans gradually lost authority over the course of time, which allowed the Russians, who had grown more powerful in the north, to strengthen their influence in the region. has been.

The fact that the Caucasus is a passage point for the warm waters is the primary reason for Russia's interest in the area. Because of this circumstance, Russia became interested in this area throughout subsequent time periods. The Russian government's policies toward the area unequivocally demonstrated its power, particularly up to the 19th century. Especially significant for Russia is the significance of the Ottoman-Russian Wars: By establishing authority in the countries of Crimea and Georgia, first the dominion of the Black Sea and later the continuation of expansionism towards the warm seas may be accomplished. (Iron, 1998). Georgia became independent from the Ottoman Empire with the signing of the Kucuk Kaynarca Agreement in 1774. The Georgiyevsk Agreement, which took place in 1783, established Georgia's connection to Russia. After the Bolshevik Revolution in Russia in 1917, the societies in the Caucasus proclaimed their independence by taking advantage of the disarray that ensued; nonetheless, they were eventually forced to surrender to the dominance of the Soviet Union. During its brief era of independence from 1918 to 1921, Georgia was not powerful enough to keep its independence and was unable to find the perfect conjuncture to keep its freedom. As a result, Georgia lost its independence. According to Gul (2009), during this historical period the Georgian people had a difficult time. Following the conclusion of the First World War, on March 12, 1922, Georgia became a member of the Transcaucasian Soviet Federative Republic. Four years later, in 1936, Georgia became a part of the Soviet Union, which contributed to Russia's increased military influence in the Caucasus area.

In the course of and after the fight for independence, Georgia had the objective of establishing diplomatic ties with Turkey. This was done with the goal of relieving the pressure exerted by Russia and gaining the assistance of Turkey. (Cakmak, 1998) reports that when the Georgian ambassador to Turkey, Simeon Medivani, gave his letter of credence to Ankara, he declared that he desired for Turkey to attack Georgia in order to free Georgia from Russian control. Following this, Turkey requested that Georgia hand up Artvin and Ardahan in line with the Brest-Litovsk Agreement, and it then proceeded to regain control of these provinces. In Batumi, Turkish forces seized the territory, and Kazim Karabekir was the commander in charge of them. Batumi, on the

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other hand, was ceded to the Soviet Union as part of the Moscow Agreement of 1921. This was due to the fact that the Georgians had handed up control of the territory to the Russians and that Georgia's military might was insufficient. The Kars Agreement, which was signed in 1922 by Georgia, Azerbaijan, and Armenia, established Turkey's eastern boundary once and for all.

A Cold War That Lasted a Long Time in The Period of Two Countries Between Any One of Them

In the Sense That It Is Impossible to Speak. Because the federal republics that were part of the USSR were required to live under the stringent supervision of the central authority of the USSR, they did so. On the other hand, Georgia announced its independence on April 9, 1991, after the conclusion of the Cold War. The ties between Georgia and Turkey, which was one of the first nations to recognize Georgia's independence on December 16, 1991, are beginning to heat up again. Turkey was one of the first countries to do so.

In the years after the conclusion of the Cold War, ties between Turkey and the United States have undergone a significant degree of convergence. It is fair to say that the United States has a greater level of influence over Turkey now, particularly in light of the First Gulf War and the tight relationship that Turgut Ozal, who served as Turkey's Prime Minister at that time, had with the United States. In point of fact, the United States of America desired to cultivate positive ties with Georgia by capitalizing on the tensions that existed between Georgia and the Russian Federation during the latter's fight for independence. To this aim, they made an effort to exert their influence on Turkey in this regard. When seen from this angle, the foreign policy that the United States has pursued in a significant area such as the Caucasus is an aspect of international relations that simply cannot be ignored.

Putting the time of disconnection during the USSR era to one side, it is clear that the interactions between Turks and Georgians truly have a very extensive and deep historical past. This is true despite the fact that the two groups were cut off from one another during the USSR era. Nevertheless, a third power has never been absent from this interaction between the two countries. In this regard, in Georgian-Turkish interactions, it is fairly feasible to come across influences from other cultures like as the Eastern Romans, Mongolians, Iranians, and Russians. Because of all of these many connections, the Caucasus region's placement on the earth's surface has a significant

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amount of significance. The Caucasus has served as both a transitional and important point for opening up to new geographical areas, as well as a buffer zone for governments that aspire to be the dominating force in the region, where they can protect themselves from any potential threats. It would be useful to examine the ways in which geography has played a significant influence in the development of history as it relates to Turkey and Georgia.

The primary objective of this study is to investigate the impact that the presence of the Turkish population has had on the political ties between Turkey and Georgia. The following research questions will each have their respective answers provided by this study:

- (1) *Turkey-Georgia historical relations?*
- (2) *Turkey-Georgia economic relationship?*
- (3) *What is the importance of the Ahiska region for the two countries?*
- (4) *Ahiska the reason for the exile of the Turks and its effects today?*
- (5) *Ahiska what are the current status and problems of Turkey?*

In order to conduct this study, the approach that will be employed will consist of data collecting and analysis. The research team read and studied a wide variety of scholarly publications and books that were authored in this topic. The findings of this study, which are abbreviated as Ahiska. This will provide light on the significance of Turkey with regard to both nations from the Taman Peninsula, which is found in the eastern portion of the Black Sea, to the Caspian Sea, which is situated in the western section of the region. Ahiska to the peninsula makes up a significant portion of the one which... hilly area is dubbed the "Caucasus" (Ciloglu, 1999 4). Date One of the migratory routes the Turks use to go to Anatolia is via Georgian Caucasia, which is both a settled territory and a mountainous one. In this regard, the connection between Georgians and Turks may be traced all the way back to the earliest and most undocumented Turkish migrations (Ciloglu, 1993). For Turks, the Caucasus has long been a strategically significant territory. The Caucasus has taken on the responsibility of acting as a natural border post against any assaults that may originate from the north. This is especially important in terms of ensuring the safety of Anatolia, which is considered to be the heartland of the nation, and preserving the state's authority over the integrity of its territory. According to Saray (1997), the Turks, who always aimed to build good

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ties with the Muslim peoples residing in this area, wanted to get along well with the Georgians who lived in the Caucasus owing to their geographical closeness. This was due to the fact that the Caucasus and Turkey are geographically close to one another. However, Russia, which expanded its endeavors towards the area after the 16th century, first undermined the supremacy of the Turks over the Caucasus, and then entirely killed off the Turks' control over the territory.

Anatolia has been the site of several power struggles and attempts at unification and control throughout Turkish history. Even at times when the Turks were at their most powerful in Anatolia, the dangers posed by the Caucasus, which is the natural extension of Anatolia, did not lessen (Demir, 2003). In point of fact, Turkish sovereignty in Anatolia was harmed as a result of invasions by both the Mongols and the Russians. In light of this, it is essential to cultivate positive relationships with the people who make up this area in order to lessen the risk posed by the potential dangers that may emanate from it. Although the Caucasus is a significant territory in terms of Anatolian dominance, Anatolia has also been an essential location for the peoples of the Caucasus, who have been forced to live between the tides of north-south power balances. It is vitally crucial for Georgians, in particular, that there be a balance of power between the south and the north. In some eras of Georgian history, the Georgians attempted to maintain a power balance between the north and the south by, at times, attempting to get the upper hand in both regions, and at other times, doing the exact reverse. Because of this, connections between Anatolia and the Caucasus have remained constant throughout history, with the exception of the time period including the Cold War.

After the dissolution of the Soviet Union, the 610 kilometers of border that formerly separated the USSR and Turkey are now dispersed along the borders of Nakhchivan, Armenia, and Georgia. The length of the Georgian and Turkish borders is 276 kilometers. The region of Turkey that is located north of this boundary is called the North East. Turkey places a significant amount of attention on the Georgian border as a result of the hostile ties that exist between it and Armenia. Gunal (1997) states that this boundary sits on both the Asian and Turkish continents. Relationships between the states and the one which... and also Turkey's. At the juncture of opening up to the Caucasus, significant opportunities present themselves. On the other hand, Georgia places a significant amount of weight on Turkey's border in terms of the country's opening up to Europe and ensuring

its own safety. In addition, this border serves as a focal point for both the economic and investment partnerships that exist between the two nations on each side of it.

When we take into account the circumstances of the present day and examine Turkey's connections to Central Asia, the Caucasus once again emerges as a very significant geographical axis. In terms of the physical closeness between Georgia and Turkey, as well as the political aspirations between the two nations, Georgia acts as a unifying factor in the geopolitics of both Anatolia and the Caucasus. Both the Georgians who live in Turkey as well as the Muslims who live in Georgia are an important part of the cultural interchange that plays a vital role in the process of bringing the two nations closer together.

Ordu, Sinop, Kocaeli, Artvin, Giresun, Adapazari (Sakarya), and Samsun are the provinces in Turkey where the majority of the Georgian people who migrated to Turkey settled. Due to the fact that the majority of Georgians are Muslims, they are sometimes referred to as "Acar." The Muslims of Georgian ancestry who live in the Adjarian Autonomous Region inside the boundaries of Georgia are known by the moniker Acarlar. It is possible to meet a significant number of persons of Georgian heritage who have the surname "Acar" in Turkey.

1- Political and Economic Relations

The East-West corridor idea is an alternate energy transfer route for the European Union, which seeks to get rid of its energy reliance. The Turkey-Azerbaijan-Georgia ties have a significant role in the concept, and their importance cannot be overstated.

Figure-1 East-West Energy Corridor

Source: Biresselioglu (2012)

The Baku-Tbilisi-Ceyhan oil pipeline, the Baku-Tbilisi-Erzurum natural gas pipeline and TANAP, the Baku-Tbilisi-Kars railway and road projects are all significant in terms of demonstrating the level of collaboration that has been achieved between Turkey, Georgia, and Azerbaijan.

Figure-2 Train and Road Projects

Source: (Sandikli, 2014)

In 2013, the foreign ministers of the three countries met twice. In the last 10 For many years, the most prominent topic in Turkey and Georgia's diplomatic ties has been Turkey's and Georgia's respective efforts to expand their bilateral economic ties and Georgia's and Turkey's respective efforts to maximize their collaboration by lowering the administrative hurdles that stand in the way of investments in both countries. In 2006, as a result of the closing of the Russian market to Georgian goods, the intensity of commercial relations between the two countries reached its maximum level, with Georgia giving significant prospects to Turkish businessmen in this respect. This was owing to the fact that Georgia had closed its market to Russian products. Tbilisi and Batumi Airports, both of which were constructed by TAV Airports Holding, have in point of fact had their operation rights sold to Turkish businesses for a period of twenty years.

Figure-3 Pipeline Projects

Source: (Sandikli 2014)

The free trade agreement between Turkey and Georgia was signed in 2007, and the visa-free travel application has been in effect since 2005. Additionally, the passport-free travel application has been in effect since 2012, which has contributed to the growing breadth of commercial ties between Turkey and Georgia. Additionally, there was a discernible rise in the quantity of visitors coming to Georgia from Turkey. In 2012, Turks made up 39 percent of all visitors that traveled to Georgia. There are certain difficulties that are having a detrimental impact on the path of relations between Turkey and Georgia, despite the hopeful attitude that exists between the two countries. During the conflict between Russia and Georgia in 2008, Turkey took a stance that would not disturb Russia, did not allow the passage of United States warships or hospital ships by strictly applying the provisions of the Montreux Convention, relations with the European Union came to a standstill, and the positive relations that were tried to be developed with Armenia for a while caused a negative perception of Turkey from the Georgian side.

The elections that took place in Georgia in 2012 brought to light a number of opinions and sentiments that are unfavorable toward Turkey. Some politicians in Georgia have begun to question the state of their country's ties with Turkey as a result of Turkey's rising economic weight in Georgia's economy, the growth in the number of schools and mosques in Georgia, and the neglect of Georgian churches in the north-eastern region of Turkey.

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continue in the direction of overlooking Ahiska. In addition, the ruined Batumi Aziziye Mosque will be reconstructed in the city of Batumi if the authorities of Georgia decide to allot some property for that purpose. In exchange for the restoration work done in Georgia, two churches in Turkey—the Ishan Church in Artvin and the Osvank Church in Erzurum Uzundere will have their interiors renovated. The majority of the restoration that began in 2012 and was carried out under the supervision of Georgian specialists has been finished.

The political relations between the two countries are improving, and with them come improvements in the economic and commercial ties that bind the two nations together. Since 2007, Turkey has become Georgia's most important commercial partner thanks to the ratification of the Free Trade Agreement between the two countries. With this number, Turkey's stake in Georgia's total foreign commerce reached 16.5%. In this scenario, the amount of trade between the two countries in 2010 was 1.104 billion dollars. Additionally, the whole worth of the projects that were carried out in Georgia by Turkish contractors was greater than one billion dollars. In recent years, it has been clear that Turkish enterprises have a significant position and play an important role, particularly in the building of hydroelectric power facilities. On the other hand, the total amount of money that our nation invested in Georgia between the years 1997 and 2010 was 682.3 million dollars. In a similar vein, Turkish businesspeople have invested more than one billion dollars in the construction of fourteen hydroelectric power facilities. Contracting firms from Turkey have successfully completed over 160 projects in Georgia, the majority of which were infrastructure-related and had a total value of \$3 billion.

Figure-4 Import/Export Volume

years	EXPORT	IMPORTS	VOLUME	BALANCE
2017	1,209	215	1,424	994
2018	1,315	234	1,549	1,081
2019	1,578	272	1,850	1,305

2018-2019 %	20	16.5	19.4	20.7
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Source: TR Ministry of Commerce official site

2-Athiska Turks Issue

2.1. Ahiska Region And Its Importance

Georgia is a hilly area that is located between 12 and 30 kilometers from the border with Turkey. This area is sometimes referred to as "Meskhetia" and "Ahiska-Jawaheti" (Avsar et al., 1995). The areas of Ahiska and Ahilkelek, which are located in the east of the Adjara Autonomous Republic, in the northeast of Turkey, bordering with the province of Ardahan, and in the southwest of Tbilisi, are now a part of Georgia but were formerly a very important part of Turkey. (Arslan, 1997). It is situated on the left bank of the Kur River, which flows to the north of the Kars province (Kirzioglu, 1970). The Gole district of Kars is the place where the river's headwaters may be found. 15 kilometers away from the Turkish border lies the city of Ahiska, which serves as the hub for more than two hundred villages and key communities including Abastuban, Adigan, Aspinza, Ahilkelek, Azgur, and Hidirz. This city is situated in the middle of the region. In the southwestern part of Georgia, you'll find this area that shares a border with Turkey (Yuzbey, 2008).

Gehir is a town that can be reached by road from Tbilisi, Batumi, and Turkey. It is situated on both banks of the Posof Stream. In addition, Tbilisi and Ahiska are linked by a railway that continues on to the town of Vale, which is located quite near to the border with Turkey. Agriculture can be practiced successfully on the arable lands that are irrigated by the Kur River, the Posof and Adigan Streams, and the streams that mix with these rivers and streams.

Ahiska-Cavaheti, also known as Samtshe-Cavaheti, is the name given to the Ahiska area under the contemporary administrative framework. The Ahiska-Jawaheti Province is made up of the Ahiska, Adigan, Aspinza, and Borcom districts that formerly belonged to the Ahiska Province, as well as the Ahilkelek and Nimotsminda districts that formerly belonged to the Cavahet Province. According to Kanbolat (2000), the new province has a total land area of 6413 km², and it contains 7 towns and 250 villages that are organized into 6 districts.

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The geographical features of Ahiska set it apart from the rest of the nation in several respects. This location has been referred to as "Georgia's Siberia" as a result of the heavy snowfall that lasted for around six months and the very severe environment that reached temperatures as low as -20 degrees. Cavahet is situated on a plateau above the mountains, and it is flanked on all sides by dormant volcanoes. Ahilkelek is located above, and it is 1750 meters above sea level. A number of Nimotsminda's settlements are located at an elevation of 2,000 meters above sea level. comes first.

The strategic importance of the Ahiska-Cavahet region can be broken down into several categories, including the following:

- Serving as a link between Turkey and the Caucasus, the Idil-Ural Region, and Turkistan;

- Bringing together the whole of Turkey in terms of its geographical position between Adjara and Borcali,
- When viewed from the directions of Georgia-Azerbaijan, Armenia, and Turkey, it has an operation area that extends in three different directions;
- Due to its proximity to the province of Ardahan, the city of
- This region is significant because it is where the Turkgozu border gates in Posof and the Aktas border gates in Cildir are opened.
- Turkey's proximity to Armenia, which poses the greatest security risk to it in the Caucasus region;
- Kars-Tbilisi Railway Project; European Transport Corridor Project; Baku-Tbilisi-Ceyhan Transport Corridor Project;

Being on the routes of energy and transportation projects that go through the Caucasus and where we have important national interests, such as the HPBH Project and the Baku-Tbilisi-Erzurum DGBH project, gives us an advantage. These projects include:

- Once more than 25,000 Meskhetian Turks have made Turkey their home, Turkey has earned the right to exercise political leadership in the Caucasus region.

2.2. The Origin of Ahiska Turks

In the year 1068, the districts of Meskhetia and Tbilisi that had been captured by Sultan Alparslan were given over to the hands of the Orthodox Turks. These Orthodox Turks originated from beyond the Caucasus and expanded to the Kur and Coruh tribes. According to Tasdemir (2005), it is well

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known that many Kipchak tribes and tribes completely absorbed this territory in the 12th century. In Georgia, the Kipchaks founded principalities that were associated with the Iranians and the Ilkhanids. They had a significant amount of power in the state and army administration. In 1578, after the Ottoman Empire's invasion of Georgia, Turks, specifically picked from the provinces of Konya, Tokat, and Yozgat, were placed in Ahiska and its surrounding areas, and as a result, this area developed into a wholly Turkish homeland (Mert, 2004). According to Kirzioglu (1953), the city of Ahiska is one of the eleven sanjaks that make up the province of Cildir, which was founded after the Ottoman Empire was defeated. At the same time, Meskhetian is the heart of this province, and this circumstance persisted for almost two hundred and fifty years. When the Russians first arrived in the Caucasus in 1801, they immediately took control of this territory and ruled it. During the Ottoman-Russian war of 1828, the Russians marched all the way to Erzurum after seizing Kars and Ahiska. Even though they were evacuated with the 1829 Edirne Treaty, Meskhetian was given to the Russians as a war recompense (Zeyrek, 2013). The Moscow and Kars Agreements of 1921 were reached shortly after, and they totally severed the area from Turkey. It then became a part of the territory of Georgia. This region had been caught between the crosscurrents of political currents.¹

2.3. The Issue of Export of Ahiska Turks

After the Ottoman-Russian War in 1828–1829, the Russians were given control of the Meskhetian territory. This was the beginning of the issue with the Meskhetian Turks, which has persisted up until the present day. During the Ottoman-Russian conflict that took place between 1853 and 1856, some of the Meskhetian Turks who had been persecuted by Tsarist Russia for their assistance to the Ottoman army sought sanctuary in the Ottoman Empire. Following the loss of the Ottoman Empire at the hands of the Russian Empire in the war that lasted from 1877 to 1878, massive migrations of people from the Caucasus to Anatolia occurred as a consequence. Tanriverdi (2017) suggests that the political, religious, and economic environments each played a significant part in

¹ For more information on the border change of the Ahiska region, see. Ayna Askarova (Askeroğlu), "Determination of the South Caucasus Boundaries in the Conferences Period (Trabzon, Batumi, Istanbul)", **Caucasian File**, History and Nature Foundation Publications, Istanbul 2006, pp.151-182; Ayna Askeroğlu Arslan, "Moscow Agreement and Turkey's North-East Border", **Trakya University Journal of Social Sciences**, Vol. 17/2, Trakya University Press, Edirne 2015. p. 1-20.

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these migrations. To highlight some of these aspects: Meskhetian Turks were subjected to harsh treatment at the hands of Georgians and Armenians during the First World War, which took place from 1914 to 1918. The Soviet Union began a campaign of extreme repression and brutality against the Meskhetian Turks in 1921, and it continued till now. Despite their lack of combat experience, about 40,000 Meskhetian Turks were sent to the front lines as soon as the Second World War broke out, despite the fact that they had not been recruited until after that conflict had already begun. During the fight, around 25,000 Meskhetian Turks are killed, and many more are wounded or crippled.

According to Zeyrek (2013), the Stalin Government's objective is to expel the Meskhetian Turks from the territories they have historically inhabited. According to Uren (2016) and other sources, on November 14, 1944, Stalin gave the order for the Ahiska people to be forcefully taken from their houses throughout the night, loaded onto freight wagons within a few hours of that night, and then deported to Siberia, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, and Uzbekistan. The number of Ahiska people who were sent into exile is believed to be between 115,000 and 138,000. When this figure is combined to the 40,000 Ahiska children and young adults who were sent off to the front lines during the Second World War, the total number of Ahiska people who were forced into exile comes to 180 thousand. Thousands of Ahiska people who were exiled to a distant land perished on the way there because of the harsh conditions they endured, including the cold, starvation, and several other unpleasant conditions. Peoples from the Caucasus, such as the Ingushes, Karachay, and Chechens, were also forced into exile together with the Meskhetian Turks. The Meskhetian Turks, who were forced into exile and kept under surveillance in the nations to which they were deported, were doomed to a harsh and trying existence due to the varied environmental conditions of the locations to which they were sent.

As a result of the tragic events that took place in the Fergana area of Uzbekistan in 1989, the Meskhetian Turks were forced to flee their homeland for the second time. The violent events that took place between Uzbeks and Meskhetian Turks in April 1989 resulted in the deaths of hundreds of people and left a trail of bloodshed in their wake. Meskhetian Turks were forced to leave this territory together with everyone else in order to preserve the social harmony. Over one hundred thousand Meskhetian Turks left their homeland and settled in the interior regions of Russia and the Krasnodar area, as well as in Azerbaijan, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, and Turkmenistan.

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Meskhetian Turks, who had previously relocated to the Krasnodar area of Russia, were forced to leave this region as well owing to the pressure of radical Russian nationalism. As a result, they looked for a new place to live and came to the United States, relying on the residency permission issued to them by the government of the United States.

After being driven from their homes and lands in 1944, the Ahiska people are now spread among a large number of locations around the globe. Meskhetian Turks, whose total population is believed to be close to 600,000, reside as immigrants in 10-15 nations and approximately 100 areas around the world today. Meskhetian Turks, the majority of whom reside in countries that were a part of the Soviet Union in the past, are mostly located in Kazakhstan, the Russian Federation, Azerbaijan, Turkey, Kyrgyzstan, Uzbekistan, and Ukraine. This is because of the historical connections between these countries. Even though Georgia's discourse regarding the return of Meskhetian Turks to their homeland has become more lenient since the fall of the Soviet Union, and Georgia has even committed to the solution of the Meskhetian Turks problem with some international agreements, it appears that the problem has been prolonged by citing economic and political reasons. It is decided to implement a program that will leave them behind, and the Meskhetian Turks will not be permitted to return for a variety of reasons that are not fully explained.

The legislation that was passed in 1992 (with the date 2.7.1992 and the number 835) about the admission and resettlement of Meskhetian Turks in Turkey promoted the migration of Meskhetian Turks residing in various places throughout the globe to Turkey. By passing this legislation, it was established that Turkey would annually take in a certain quota of Turks originally from Meskhetia. After the ordinance was passed, around two hundred Ahiska Turkish families were granted permission to go to Turkey and settled in the Iğdir region. Families had all of their many requirements satisfied, including those pertaining to housing, employment, education, and social security. Those who arrived, with the exception of those who were already established there, mostly established themselves independently in large cities such as Bursa, Istanbul, Ankara, Kocaeli, Izmir, and Antalya. After 1992, Bursa has been one of the provinces that people want to migrate to the most.

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3. Contemporary Status and Problems of Ahiska Turks

The following is a list of the requests that the Meskhetian Turks, who were forced into exile as a result of the Second World War, have made to the Republic of Turkey:

1. Immediate execution of the Law number. 3835 on the Admission and Settlement of Ahiska Turks, which was enacted by the Grand National Assembly of Turkey on July 2, 1992, and the decision number. 376, which was made by the Government of the Republic of Turkey in 1992, 1.
2. To assist Meskhetian Turks who have immigrated to Turkey since 1990 with their citizenship applications, and to promptly grant the right of Turkish Citizenship and Dual Citizenship to Meskhetian Turks who have immigrated to Turkey since 1990; Establishing a coordination and reaching an agreement between the governments of the United States of America, Russia, Ukraine, Azerbaijan, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Uzbekistan, and Georgia, and the government of the Republic of Turkey, regarding the rights of Mesk
3. The immediate issuance of work licenses and residency authorizations to Turks from Meskhetia who have freely relocated to Turkey
4. Making it easier for Ahiska Turks, many of whom are medical professionals, engineers, educators, and other types of professions, to get equivalent for the credentials they have already earned from the Council of Higher Education;
5. Establishment of a commission, including representatives of Ahiska, by the Government of the Republic of Turkey in order to promptly solve the education, health, employment, housing, and social security problems of Ahiska Turks living in the United States of America, Russia, Ukraine, Azerbaijan, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Uzbekistan, and Georgia. This commission is to be established both in Turkey and abroad. As a direct consequence of the efforts put forward by the aforementioned commission, an understanding has been established between the governments of the United States of America, Russia, Ukraine, Azerbaijan, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Uzbekistan, and Georgia, as well as the government of the Republic of Turkey, regarding a number of issues pertaining to regional security.
6. Ahiska Turkish children living in the United States of America, Russia, Ukraine, Azerbaijan, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Uzbekistan, and Georgia to receive education at universities in Turkey through the Turkish Cooperation and Development Administration, YOK, and other relevant

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institutions. as well as to promptly boost the number of slots that have been set aside for Ahiska Turkish students,

7. When Georgia became a member of the Council of Europe in 1999, the subject of the Ahiska Turks returning to their homeland in Georgia, the Meskhetian region, came to the forefront. In accordance with the principles of international law, the Georgian government has promised to allow the Ahiska Turks to settle inside its borders up to the year 2011. The Ahiska Turks, whose population is estimated to be over 500,000 and who reside mostly in Turkey, are, on the other hand, dispersed throughout the United States, Russia, Ukraine, Azerbaijan, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Uzbekistan, and Georgia, and the challenges they confront are becoming more severe on a daily basis. In this view, the government of Turkey should facilitate an agreement between the relevant nations and Georgia that would allow the Meskhetian Turks to reside in the Meskhetian area, which is territory that rightfully belongs to them.

8. The Turkish Republic government should take steps in the European Union, the Council of Europe, the United Nations, the Organization for Security and Cooperation in Europe (OSCE), and any other international bodies in order to preserve the rights of Ahiska Turks and swiftly address their concerns.

When Georgia joined the Council of Europe in 1999, it took on the responsibility of fulfilling a duty for the repatriation of Meskhetian Turks at that time. According to this, Georgia would begin the process of returning the Ahiska people within two years after the year 1999 and would complete the procedure within those two years, which would be in 2011. Meskhetian Turks might take Georgia to the European Court of Human Rights and demand that they be allowed to return to their homeland if the country failed to fulfill its responsibilities at the conclusion of the time. The return processes for Meskhetian Turks required the enactment of a legislation as well as the submission of the requisite applications; however, the process was complicated by the low number of applications submitted in accordance with the return law and the virtually complete absence of applications submitted by Russia. The incapacity of the Ahiska people to maintain a completely ordered society is the root cause of this problem. Requests to extend the time limit were accommodated, but the mobility that was anticipated did not materialize. The fact that Georgia provides our Ahiska inhabitants with a variety of different reasons is another factor contributing to this stagnation. The following are examples of some of these:

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1. The homeland of the Ahiska people is currently inhabited by people of Armenian and Georgian descent. Therefore, Georgia contends that if the Ahiska people return, the required resettlement will not be supplied, the area will not be able to manage such a movement, and anarchy would ensue. In addition, Georgia claims that the region will not be able to handle such a migration.

2. The Ahiska people have staked a claim to the areas they inhabited before to their exile; however, the Armenians, who now hold title to a large portion of the territory in question, are vehemently opposed to these requests. Because Georgia does not want this issue to negatively impact its relationship with Armenia, it has made it very difficult for the Ahiska people to go through the necessary steps to get their land back.

3. One of the most significant challenges that Ahiska Turks are confronted with is the fact that it is very hard for a group that has been exiled to secure the appropriate official paperwork throughout the process of returning home.

4. The Armenian diaspora's assertions that "Ahiska people who have returned to their homeland will demand a union with Turkey" cause Georgia to feel concerned.

5. A top Georgian official has been quoted as saying that the present Georgian administration has shown a desire to expedite the legal procedure by which Meskhetian Turks may get Georgian citizenship. According to David Darakhvelidze, the Minister of Refugees and Resettlement, 8,900 Meskhetian Turks have submitted applications for citizenship up to this point, and 5,841 of those applications have been authorized for scrutiny. There were 1,053 individuals who were awarded citizenship. It is anticipated that the newly elected administration would take steps in 2012 to streamline the citizenship process and provide financial support to those who have left the country. In a similar vein, Meskhetian Turks who now reside in Georgia and have the ability to apply for citizenship are contemplating leaving the nation due to the deplorable state of their financial circumstances.

The processes for acquiring Georgian citizenship were required to be finished by the end of 2011 in accordance with the responsibilities that Georgia accepted when it joined the Council of Europe in 1999 and the legislative arrangements that were formed after the country joined. Only 6,000 out of the approximately 300,000 Meskhetian Turks residing outside of Georgia filed for citizenship in 2010, the year when the Georgian government stopped accepting applications. It's generally

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agreed that the drawn-out nature of bureaucratic processes is to blame for the low number of applicants. However, it is evident that there will not be a major rise in the number of persons who desire to return if no measures are done to find solutions to the difficulties associated with settling in and finding work.

Georgia has extended, at Turkey's urging, the application time that is provided in the statute of return. This extension was made possible by Turkey. Within this context, it was decided that Turkey would pay the wages of the five people who were sent to Georgia for a period of six months to be inspected by Turkey. This was done in order to speed up the assessment phase. Close communication was created with the Georgian authorities in order to speed up the evaluation phase. On July 11, 2007, a draft legislation regarding the repatriation and integration of Meskhetian Turks into their homeland was approved by the Georgian parliament. President Saakashvili signed the measure, and it subsequently became a statute of the country. Nonetheless, the conflict that broke out between Russia and Georgia in 2008 caused a delay in the implementation of the legislation (<http://www.tbmm.gov.tr/>, 23.5.2014).

The return of Meskhetian Turks is not something that is well received in Georgia. The settlement of Meskhetians and Turkish-Muslims is seen as a danger to the future of Georgia by the Georgian authorities, particularly in areas close to the border with Turkey. On the other side, the Georgian government does not take a constructive stance toward the allegations that the Ahiska people have made.

The geopolitical, economic, and cultural ties that bind Turkey and Georgia together form the basis of their relations. The two nations' political conversation and cooperative efforts are continually becoming closer to one another. Georgia benefits from Turkey's financial assistance, while Turkey also helps Georgia's efforts to integrate into the European Union. In the context of the ties between Turkey and Georgia, the topic of the status of the Meskhetian Turks has also been brought up for discussion. The problem of the status of the Meskhetian Turks in Georgia was brought to the attention of international forums by Turkey, which maintained the rights of those people living there.

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Conclusion

The Meskhetian Turks are a Turkish ethnic minority that has struggled throughout history due to a variety of factors. After being forced into exile by the Soviet Union, the Meskhetian Turks eventually formed an integral element of the political connections that exist between Turkey and Georgia. Turkey provided assistance for the Meskhetian Turks by protecting their rights and bringing the status problem of Meskhetian Turks residing in Georgia to the forefront of the discussion. Turkey's efforts in this area enhance the expectations of Meskhetian Turks for a brighter future. The status of Meskhetian Turks has been a significant element in Turkey's ties with Georgia, and these relations have been strained in the past.

The geopolitical, economic, and cultural ties that bind Turkey and Georgia together form the basis of their relations. The two nations' political conversation and cooperative efforts are continually becoming closer to one another. Georgia benefits from Turkey's financial assistance, while Turkey also helps Georgia's efforts to integrate into the European Union. In the context of the ties between Turkey and Georgia, the topic of the status of the Meskhetian Turks has also been brought up for discussion. The problem of the status of the Meskhetian Turks in Georgia was brought to the attention of international forums by Turkey, which maintained the rights of those people living there.

The predicament that the Meskhetian Turks find themselves in is one that has attracted the attention of the world community. Numerous nations and international organizations have engaged in a wide range of activities in an effort to assist efforts to find a solution to the status issue and to safeguard the rights of Meskhetian Turks. In addition to the efforts being spearheaded by Turkey, the European Union, the United Nations, and other human rights groups have also brought attention to the plight of Meskhetian Turks and stated their support for finding a solution to the problem.

The recent improvement in ties that have taken place between Turkey and Georgia makes the process of Meskhetian Turks moving back to their homeland easier. However, in the process of returning Meskhetian Turks to their homeland after being unjustly removed from their lands and dispersed all over the world, the fact that the Georgian administration did not take any concrete steps in terms of property and collective life revealed that the process was moving very slowly. This was a problem because the process involved returning Meskhetian Turks to their homeland. In this view, Turkey should continue its diplomatic measures with Georgia, which is on the transit

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route to Azerbaijan and Central Asia, in order to guarantee that Meskhetian Turks may return to their country under decent circumstances. Georgia is located on the path. Even though the presence of an Armenian population in the area known as Ahiska makes the process of returning to Meskheta more difficult, Turkey is strengthening its relations with the Caucasus through its economic and political arguments, the return of Meskhetian Turks to their homeland, and in this sense is continuing to seek solutions both for Meskhetian species and for a solution. In addition to this, it is essential for the purpose of strengthening the relationships that will be built with Central Asia.

As a consequence of this, the role of Meskhetian Turks in the political ties between Turkey and Georgia has become more significant as a direct result of Turkey's support and efforts in the international arena. Protecting the rights of Meskhetian Turks and finding a solution to the status issue is a crucial step toward ensuring the continuation of positive ties between Turkey and Georgia as well as maintaining peace in the area. The assistance of Turkey and the international community is very vital at this point, as the dreams of the Meskhetian Turks for a brighter future continue to grow.

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